

“I’m not that bad in maths after all”: The Influence of Rich Tasks on Primary Students’ Learning in Mathematics

Tandeep Kaur¹, Eilish McLoughlin², Paul Grimes¹

¹Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning and School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies, Dublin City University ²Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning and School of Physical Sciences, Dublin City University

This study reports on the implementation of rich tasks designed to enhance student learning in mathematics at primary level. This study was conducted over a five-month period, involving 113 sixth-class students (aged 11-12 years) in a primary school in Ireland. Ten rich tasks were designed and implemented that were aligned with the primary mathematics curriculum and supported the development of students’ productive dispositions in mathematics. The design principles used for developing these rich tasks in mathematics are discussed and exemplified. Semi-structured interviews were carried out with three teachers that collaborated with the researchers on facilitating the implementation of these tasks. This study discusses the teachers’ experiences of implementing rich tasks in mathematics and their perceptions of the influence of these tasks on their students’ learning. The teachers developed their understanding of the role of rich tasks in mathematics. The teachers identified that the use of rich tasks provided opportunities for students to develop their mathematical thinking, as well as fostering positive student attitudes and engagement in mathematics.

Keywords: Rich tasks, Primary mathematics, Mathematics learning, Productive disposition

Introduction

Research highlights a decline in students’ motivation and interest for learning mathematics as they progress in levels of education (Deieso & Fraser, 2019; Widlund et al., 2018). As a result, they develop negative attitudes towards mathematics (Yao et al., 2018). These negative attitudes can strongly impede the development of students’ mathematical identities and impact on their academic progression. A critical construct that significantly influences young learners’ engagement in and attitudes towards mathematics is their productive disposition. Productive disposition is defined as ‘the tendency to see sense in mathematics, to perceive it as both useful and worthwhile, to believe that steady effort in learning mathematics pays off, and to see oneself as an effective learner and doer of mathematics’ (NRC, 2001, p. 131). In other words, productive disposition is a positive outlook towards mathematics that enables a person to put effort in solving a mathematical task with the belief that the problem can be solved. Teachers’ instructional practices and classroom learning environment are key factors in shaping students’ attitudes and dispositions for learning (Kaur et al., 2022).

Students with a productive disposition exhibit curiosity and a willingness to explore and extend their learning (NRC, 2001). However, the domain of productive dispositions has received little attention, as it is not as easily accessible and measurable as other domains of learning (Grady, 2016). Furthermore, common pedagogical practices employed in mathematics provide less opportunities to develop productive dispositions (Ally & Christiansen, 2013).

Rich tasks have been identified as a valuable approach for designing mathematics activities that address students' learning needs and interests (Bobis et al., 2021). Rich tasks refer to authentic learning opportunities that are accessible to a range of students, promote productive struggle and are characterised by real-life applications of learning (Piggott, 2018; Sheffield, 2003). Several characteristics and learner outcomes of rich tasks have been identified, e.g. rich tasks have a focus on inquiry, improve questioning, promote reasoning and problem solving, encourage collaboration and provide opportunities for critical thinking (Piggott, 2018). Such tasks can provide a useful scaffolding tool to enhance student learning in cognitive, behavioural and affective domains. Careful design and implementation of rich tasks in mathematics can enrich students' learning experiences and promote positive attitudes towards the subject (Schoenfeld, 2013). With an aim to support students' mathematics learning and foster their productive dispositions in mathematics, this research took place as a task-based intervention where rich tasks were designed and implemented with students aged 11-12 years. The study was conducted over a five-month period, involving 113 sixth-class students in a primary school in Ireland. Ten rich tasks were designed and implemented that were aligned with the primary mathematics curriculum (NCCA, 2022) and supported the development of students' productive dispositions in mathematics. Semi-structured interviews were carried out with three primary teachers that collaborated with the researchers on facilitating the implementation of these tasks with the students in their classes.

This study discusses the teachers' experiences of implementing rich tasks in mathematics and their perceptions of the influence of these tasks on their students' learning and addresses the research question: *What are teachers' experiences and perceptions of the influence of rich tasks on student learning in mathematics at primary level?*

Methodology

The task design principles for this study were developed through an iterative process using an Educational Design Research (EDR) approach. EDR is a genre of research in which the iterative development of solutions to practical and complex problems provides the context for both empirical investigation and theoretical understanding (McKenney & Reeves, 2013). The process of developing task design principles matured through an amalgamation of research and practice (McKenney & Reeves, 2013). This amalgamation took place in three iterative cycles. The initial set of these design principles (Iteration 1) was developed from a synthesis of research literature on primary-secondary transition in mathematics, published during the period 1990-2020 (Kaur et al., 2022) and a review of literature around rich tasks. These design principles were refined (Iteration 2) using the data generated from a teacher professional learning programme that aimed at supporting mathematics learning across transitions (designed as part of the broader study).

Over the course of the workshops, teachers participated in discussions about the richness of tasks, engaged in co-designing rich tasks and explored the opportunities provided by a given task to enhance student learning. The continuum of richness framework drawn from Johnston-Wilder and Mason (2004) provided the basis for critical appraisal of the tasks. This framework outlines eight distinct dimensions of rich tasks where each dimension can be considered as a spectrum, ranging from routine or closed to more open or rich tasks e.g.,

tangential to essential, passive to active and closed to open. A further refinement of the iteration 2 led to the iteration 3 of task design principles, which was carried out through a) an analysis of the tasks implemented by participating teachers with their students; b) teachers' reflections on their experiences of implementing these tasks and c) the findings from the influence of these tasks on students' learning. The resulting design principles are presented in figure 1.

Figure 1

Task Design Principles

Context	Well-pitched	Meaningful and relevant	Students' personal experiences	Multiple representations
Coherence	Connection between math domains	Connection to prior knowledge	Connection with informal experiences	Sequencing activities within task
Student agency	Equitable access	Autonomy	Equity of opportunities	Accountability
Reflection	Generating discussions	Critique and argumentation	Justification	Addressing misconceptions
Adaptability	Teacher agency	Modes of presentation	Extension activities	Differentiation

An Example of a Rich Task Implemented

Students are given a route map for a shopping trail and a to-do list of several jobs (figure 2). For each job, students are required to decide the best shopping option and justify their decisions with reasoning. The task concludes with a whole class discussion on whether it is realistic to be home by the specified time, having completed the list of jobs.

This task is based on a real-life context, providing opportunities for connecting new knowledge with existing prior knowledge and informal experiences. Many students used their personal experience of travelling in a bus to estimate the time taken by the bus to cover a given distance. The element of reflection embedded within the task helped address student misconceptions. Many students changed their decisions after listening to others' ideas and reasoning. The discussion also allowed the teacher to identify the challenges that students had in completing the task and differentiate the task accordingly.

To evaluate the impact of the intervention, students' learning experiences were collected using a variety of methods such as class observations, written feedback, whole class discussions, task reflection forms, and student focus group interviews. The focus of this study is to investigate teachers' views on their experiences of implementing rich tasks and their observed influence on student learning. Semi-structured interviews with three teachers were conducted after the intervention. Data gathered from these interviews was analysed using a deductive thematic analysis.

Figure 2

Example of a Task from the Study

Findings

Influence of Rich Tasks in Fostering Productive Dispositions

Teachers appreciated student-led active learning and play-based techniques used in the tasks designed in this study. One of the observed influences of students' engagement in these tasks is a change in their outlook towards maths. In particular, for students who generally needed extra support in maths and had negative dispositions towards the subject, an increase in the level of confidence was reported.

'I think the most positive thing for me as a teacher that's come from all of this is the level of confidence that they now have in their own ability and their eagerness to actually participate'. (Teacher A)

'I found that it got the children thinking in a way that they wouldn't have done before, and they engaged in topics that they wouldn't like'. (Teacher B)

One teacher shared an example of two students in their class who received maths support and had a low self-esteem regarding their abilities in maths. Engaging in tasks that were open-ended and had multiple ways of engaging, helped them believe in their own abilities rather than comparing themselves to others in the class.

'It would literally be like you could see their insides churning and that doesn't exist at the moment because they have a little more of a positive outlook. They also realised, you know what, I might want to do the same as everyone else but in my own way, and I'm okay with that'. (Teacher A)

Another case of a student was highlighted by this teacher where the student had received maths learning support since junior infants and was so afraid of maths that she had just assumed that she was going to get it wrong. A significant increase in this students' confidence and self-esteem as a result of this intervention, was reported by the teacher.

‘With her up until this study, I would have to go down and work one to one with her for everything, even for the most simple task. And I do think that possibly maybe that's kind of a question for the level of intervention that young to do that to a child that no, it's probably not ideal. But she, I mean, she turned around and said ‘I'm not that bad in maths after all’. (Teacher A)

Long Lasting Effect of Students' Engagement

Although the intervention was for block periods during the five-month implementation of the study, the same kind of engagement was observed by teachers in their maths classes that were not part of the intervention. For instance, one teacher shared that while teaching on the topic of circles, students were asked to find the circumference of the circle without giving them the solution directly, which would normally be the case.

‘So I gave them wool. I gave them, you know, measuring equipment, all that kind of stuff... they had lots of different strategies.. So they actually were talking through many different ways of figuring it out and knowing well that there was something that they were slightly missing, but they had multiple ways of getting really close to the Circumference, which was great’. (Teacher A)

The teacher shared that before participation in the study, their students would have just reverted to looking for a direct formula or solution, but now they were more open to discovering the circumference of the given circle by trying different strategies and discussing those strategies among themselves. The element of reflection embedded within the tasks through maths talk, critiquing and listening to others' ideas, justifying, reasoning and convincing others with constructive arguments through respectful dialogue and conversations, facilitated many students to open up without the fear of getting wrong.

‘Just the way they could debate with each other that kind of stood out as well, like they were quite confident in challenging each other’. (Teacher C)

A similar effect on engagement in learning was observed in other subject areas. ‘*It's that lasting influence over that way of thinking is going across the board*’ (Teacher A). The teacher shared that those who would not usually be interested in writing or reading started to engage in conversations during their English classes.

‘It's very similar to the back and forth that they have [with] their partners in maths class. So it's kind of like they've been given that tool to hold, like, respectful dialogue about a topic and it's going into other areas as well, so I think it's a huge influence’. (Teacher A)

An interesting finding that emerged from teachers' observation is that students who the teachers would describe as previously struggling with maths, enjoyed the tasks more than those who they would describe as the higher achievers. The fact that these tasks did not have one correct answer and that a problem can be approached in multiple ways, motivated them to participate without any reservations or fears. The higher achievers (as described by the teacher), on the other hand, found it hard to engage initially as they were used to giving one concrete answer and therefore struggled more to justify and explain their solution strategies.

‘That was an eye opener to me, because two [students] in particular would be very strong at maths and would have all the questions, the competitions, any problems like that they would know how to do it. But that did, I suppose, stood out to me that they found it more difficult than the children of lower ability’. (Teacher B)

Positive Impact on Teachers’ Professional Learning

The teachers involved in the study expressed that their involvement in this study has changed the way they look at maths and their teaching practices.

‘I’ve questioned the way I have taught things in the past and how I could teach it differently and using the tasks and using your approach’. (Teacher B)

Teachers shared that the task-based intervention proved highly beneficial not only for their students but also for them as it offered professional learning for them in a practical context.

‘I just think these tasks - the rich tasks are a different level altogether and they’re very beneficial once you know we go through exactly what you’re targeting with what you want to achieve with it’. (Teacher B)

‘I’m always focusing on -It’s not the end product like it’s not the answer, it’s the process, and I think these sort of tasks highlight that further’. (Teacher C)

The cross-curricular aspect of tasks highlighted to them the significance of application of such tasks to all subject areas and to connect student learning meaningfully. Going forward, they plan to incorporate similar tasks in their classroom teaching building on the learnings from this study:

‘We’re always trying to elicit prior knowledge through conversations and stuff, but that’s one child normally speaking and all of us listening, whereas the way that [this intervention] lessons were structured was that everyone was actively engaged the whole time’. (Teacher A)

Teachers’ Reflections on the Design Features of Tasks Implemented

When discussing the tasks that were implemented in their classroom, and tasks more generally, teachers appreciated the elements of group work, maths talk, reflection, connection with other maths domains, open-endedness and the cross-curricular nature of the tasks.

‘I think it has the ability to target each different group in a classroom differently and they’ll get different outcomes of it...the lower tiers will get the confidence that there’s no right or wrong answer, But the higher achievers will get the frustration, but will actually start to think. well, you know, what’s the different ways of, you know, applying this’. (Teacher B)

The teachers commented that with opportunities for student-led learning provided by the tasks, students took more responsibility for their work than they would usually do and were eager to explore the ideas they had. In particular, the feature of maths talk was something that stood out for all the teachers and students. This is something teachers had not used earlier in their maths teaching. They also appreciated the element of reflection embedded within the tasks and the opportunities created by tasks for critique and discussion through maths talk and debates. Overall, the teachers reflected positively on their experiences of

implementing rich tasks in this study and the influence of the intervention on their students' learning. Teachers showed a willingness to continue with the use of those and similar tasks in their teaching in future.

Discussion and Conclusion

This study is an important contribution to the existing body of literature around rich tasks. Findings from teachers' interviews provide first-hand evidence of a positive impact of rich tasks on primary students' mathematics learning. Teachers reported that the use of rich tasks provided opportunities for students to develop their mathematical thinking, as well as fostering positive student attitudes and engagement in mathematics. Increased student confidence and self-esteem was also reported by the teachers. These findings are consistent with existing literature on rich tasks suggesting that rich tasks can serve as a valuable tool to enhance primary students' learning experiences in mathematics and promote productive dispositions in mathematics (Bobis et al., 2021; Schoenfeld, 2013).

This intervention also shows promise as a model of teacher professional learning, providing opportunities for teachers to reflect on their teaching practices and to inquire how and what they can do differently going forward. Teachers' experiences of implementing rich tasks based on the design principles presented in this paper, are extremely positive. The teachers developed their understanding of the role of rich tasks in mathematics and the opportunities they can provide for active student learning. A key concern identified by teachers is the time required to embed these tasks within the prescribed time-bound curriculum. Teachers commented on how the curriculum is dictated by text-book companies and the pressure to plan their teaching lessons based on the sequencing of topics according to the prescribed workbooks. These findings are consistent with how such challenges limit the time for incorporating student-led learning in their normal classroom lessons (Ingram et al., 2020). However, despite these concerns, the teachers in this study showed a willingness to incorporate rich tasks in their regular teaching practices to improve student learning in mathematics. The teachers also reflected on the importance of a learning environment in which a task is conducted. In fact, what makes a task 'rich' is the learning environment that offers opportunities for student-led learning and where students can construct their own knowledge (Piggott, 2018). Teachers shared that the tasks in this study offered a positive learning environment that helped promote students' productive dispositions towards mathematics learning.

To conclude, this study offers great potential for supporting student learning in mathematics. More specifically, the study demonstrates a shift in the belief system of students from a fixed mind-set to a growth mind-set (Boaler, 2015) and for teachers to see the value of student-led, active and inquiry-based learning through rich tasks.

References

- Ally, N., & Christiansen, I. M. (2013). Opportunities to develop mathematical proficiency in Grade 6 mathematics classrooms in KwaZulu-Natal. *Perspectives in Education*, 31(3), 106–121. Retrieved from <https://journals.ufs.ac.za/index.php/pie/article/view/1821>

- Boaler, J. (2015). *Mathematical mindsets: Unleashing students' potential through creative math, inspiring messages and innovative teaching*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bobis, J., Russo, J., Downton, A., Feng, M., Livy, S., McCormick, M., & Sullivan, P. (2021). Instructional moves that increase chances of engaging all students in learning mathematics. *Mathematics*, 9(6), 582. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9060582>
- Deieso, D., & Fraser, B. J. (2019). Learning environment, attitudes and anxiety across the transition from primary to secondary school mathematics. *Learning Environments Research*, 22(1), 133–152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-018-9261-5>
- Grady, M. (2016). Whatever Happened to Productive Disposition? *Mathematics Teaching in the Middle School*, 21(9), 516–518. <https://doi.org/10.5951/mathteacmiddscho.21.9.0516>
- Johnston-Wilder, S., & Mason, J. (Eds.). (2004). *Fundamental constructs in mathematics education*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203465387>
- Ingram, N., Holmes, M., Linsell, C., Livy, S., McCormick, M., & Sullivan, P. (2020). Exploring an innovative approach to teaching mathematics through the use of challenging tasks: a New Zealand perspective. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 32, 497-522. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13394-019-00266-1>
- Kaur, T., McLoughlin, E., & Grimes, P. (2022). Mathematics and science across the transition from primary to secondary school: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 9(1), 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-022-00328-0>
- McKenney, S., & Reeves, T. C. (2013). *Conducting educational design research*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203818183>
- National Research Council (NRC). 2001. *Adding It Up: Helping Children Learn Mathematics*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/9822>
- NCCA (2022). *Primary Mathematics Developments*. Retrieved from <https://ncca.ie/en/primary/primary-developments/stem-education/primarymathsconsultation/>
- Piggott, J. (2018). Rich tasks and contexts. NRIC: Enriching mathematics. Retrieved from <https://nrch.maths.org>
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (2013). Classroom observations in theory and practice. *ZDM*, 45, 607-621. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-012-0483-1>
- Sheffield, L. J. (2003). *Extending the challenge in mathematics: Developing mathematical promise in K-8 students*. Corwin Press.
- Widlund, A., Tuominen, H., & Korhonen, J. (2018). Academic well-being, mathematics performance, and educational aspirations in lower secondary education: Changes within a school year. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00297>
- Yao, Y., Kong, Q., & Cai, J. (2018). Investigating Elementary and Middle School Students' Subjective Well-Being and Mathematical Performance in Shanghai. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 16, 107-127. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-017-9827-1>